

Editorial

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This volume features several new and emerging scholars in TESOL and applied linguistics. It includes various topics such as peer corrective feedback, immigrant identities, teacher attitudes towards genre-based writing pedagogy, second language motivation, English Medium Instruction and intercultural communication. These diverse topics offer valuable insights for language educators and researchers alike.

OVERVIEW OF THIS VOLUME

Reports of original research

Shike Jian examines how Chinese learners' perceived proficiency levels and communication styles influence peer corrective feedback (PCF). The research, involving 27 Chinese international students at an Australian university, found no significant effect of proficiency on PCF frequency. However, hesitation linked to proficiency perceptions affected participants' positive attitudes towards PCF. The study underscores the importance of these factors in enhancing collaborative learning environments.

Yulin Zhang explores how three Chinese economic immigrants in Australia construct their identities through acculturation experiences and how this affects their investment in English learning and cross-cultural practices. Using multi-case study research and narrative enquiry, the study found that participants strongly identified with their Chinese heritage. Their perceptions of identity and capital interplay influenced their investment in English and cross-cultural activities.

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Noriko Iwashita and colleagues explore how Chinese university students cope with and perceive peer corrective feedback (PCF) during peer interaction (PI) activities. Data from 24 ESL students at an Australian university revealed that students navigate dual roles as feedback receivers and providers. They generally had positive attitudes towards PCF but varied perceptions of PI. Politeness strategies, influenced by Chinese culture, were used to maintain harmony. The study suggests that teachers should carefully consider cultural orientations and group students to enhance PI and PCF while maintaining classroom harmony.

Hideo Watanabe employs a longitudinal case study to investigate a high school language teacher's experiences with genre-based writing pedagogy in Japan. Using theoretical input and classroom observations, the study found that year-long support positively changed the teacher's attitude towards this pedagogy. Despite challenges related to the teaching environment, the use of an AI tool proved beneficial for providing corrective feedback to students.

Discussion articles

Daniel Xuqi Ouyang critically examines the Second Language Motivational Self-System (L2MSS) model, highlighting its significance and recent criticisms. The discussion includes the theoretical background, critical issues, and future research directions. The article also explores the implications of the L2MSS for language teaching research and classroom practice, providing valuable insights for educators and researchers in the field.

Interview

Jack C. Richards discusses the rise of English Medium Instruction (EMI) in educational institutions globally. He explains the reasons behind its growing popularity and contrasts it with Content and Language Integrated Learning (CLIL). Professor Richards also addresses the challenges and issues associated with EMI, providing a nuanced perspective on its impact on both educators and students. This discussion offers valuable insights for anyone interested in global education trends.

Book review

Yulia Kharchenko reviews *Teaching and Learning in English Medium Instruction* by Jack C. Richards and Jack Pun. The book covers key theories, research, and practical advice for EMI teachers, making it accessible to both secondary and

higher education settings. Its broad scope and focus on academic literacy and teaching challenges, as Kharchenko pointed out, make it a valuable resource for a wide audience, encouraging critical reflection on the impact of EMI on education.

Simon McDonald reviews Jane Jackson's third edition of *Introducing Language and Intercultural Communication*, highlighting the book's emphasis on cultural sensitivity in communication. The book argues that English fluency alone is insufficient without understanding cultural dimensions. McDonald finds the book accessible and engaging as it features vignettes and practical suggestions, making it a valuable resource for those new to intercultural communication.